

Macroeconomic Determinants of Inflation: Are Monetary and Fiscal Policies the Right Combination to Fight Inflation in Nigeria?

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Suggested Citation

Shuaibu, M., Yusufu, M., Kwajaffa, A.P., Abdullahi, S.I., & Mohammed, H.A. (2024).

Macroeconomic Determinants of Inflation: Are Monetary and Fiscal Policies the Right Combination to Fight Inflation in Nigeria? *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(4), 3-12.

DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(4\).01](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(4).01)

Abstract:

Around the world there is growing inflation since the emergence of COVID-19 and the start of Russia-Ukraine war. The COVID-19 has affected production of goods and services leading to scarcity around the world. Both Russia and Ukraine are very important in the supply of food and energy in the world. The start of war between the two countries has led to cut in the supply of food and energy around the world. This paper analyses the major determinants of inflation in Nigeria during the period 1989 to 2022. It employed cointegration analysis, granger causality test and correlation test for the analysis. It analysed the impacts of the following factors on inflation in Nigeria: money supply, foreign debt, interest rate, exchange rate, import,

export, foreign direct investment (FDI) and government expenditure. The results of the study show that inflation in Nigeria during the period of the study is as a result of monetary and fiscal policies defects; especially government's interest rate and import policies. But, during the short run the main determinants of inflation have not much effect on inflation. In order to fight the menace of inflation in Nigeria, both the CBN and the ministry of finance must join hands to fight it. Only by coordination between monetary and fiscal authorities will the problem of inflation be controlled effectively.

Keywords: *Inflation, Money Supply, Interest Rate, Exchange Rate, Government Expenditure, FDI, Cointegration, Nigeria.*

Introduction

Today in Nigeria the main question on the mouth of every Nigerian is higher prices of

goods and services. Prices of basic goods and services such as food, transport fare, water bill and energy have increased so rapidly that people are confused what to do. Price of food items

such as flour, beans and rice have multiplied from January 2023 to January 2024. Nigerian economic situation has deteriorated very much in the last 10 years. Nigeria can be said to be in a state of stagflation where higher inflation combines with economic stagnation. Around the world the same problem of inflation is being discussed by policymakers and academics. Since the outbreak of COVID-19 pandemic in 2019, the global economic is yet to return to its pandemic level of inflation. The Russian-Ukraine war and the current Middle Eastern crisis have added to the problem of inflation around the world. In Nigeria, the removal of oil subsidy and the overwhelming depreciation in the value of Naira against US dollar have combined to make the lives of Nigerians a hell.

While most developed countries have succeeded in reducing inflation into a single digit, most developing countries are struggling with the problem of inflation looking for ways to bring it down to a single digit. Single digit inflation as we can see from these developed countries is good for macroeconomic stability; while double digit inflation as we are witnessing with developing countries is disastrous for macroeconomic stability. Price stability has been the corner stone of macroeconomic policy of nations around the world. Achieving price stability is one of the key macroeconomic objectives of modern economic management. Despite government efforts to control inflation in Nigeria, inflation has become consistent problem that has become incurable. Over the years, inflation has been blame for poverty, deprivation, unemployment, deindustrialization, lack of investment and crimes in Nigeria. Nigerians are desperately looking for ways out; from increase in the value of Naira to possible price control.

The paper analyses the macroeconomic determinants of inflation in Nigeria using cointegration and granger causality methods of analysis. The study is focused on understanding drivers of inflation and why inflation research is important in Nigeria; what variables have a much influence on inflation, are these variables internal or external? The paper main objective is to determine the primary causes of inflation in Nigeria during the period of the study. It is

divided into sections and subsections; the major sectional division of the paper is as follows: introduction, literature review, methodology, discussion of results and conclusion.

What is Inflation?

According to Milton Friedman, one of the greatest monetary economists in the world in the last century, inflation refers to the general increase in prices or the money supply, both of which can cause the purchasing power of a currency to decline. But, inflation simply means general rise in the price of goods and services in an economy. When inflation is rampant it can cause lower purchasing power of money, increase in interest rate, reduction in economic growth, unemployment, increase inequality and poverty. Inflation is usually measured using consumer price index.

Inflation is also described as the general and recurrent increase in the overall level of prices for goods and services. It is measured as a yearly percentage increase. As inflation rises, every Naira one owns buys one a smaller percentage of a good or service. The value of the Naira does not remain constant during inflation. The value of a Naira can be measured in terms of purchasing power, which is the actual, tangible goods that money can buy. When inflation rises, there is usually a decline in the purchasing power of money. Inflation can be measured by the consumer price index, which reflects the yearly percentage change in the cost borne by an average consumer when they buy a basket of goods and services, which may be fixed or varied from time to time,, usually on an annual basis. The Laspeyres formula is generally used in measuring inflation (Efanga, Ugwuanyi,& Umoh, 2018).

Types and Causes of Inflation

Inflation in the modern world is a complex phenomenon that takes different forms and is caused by variant of factors. The following are major types of inflation: hyperinflation, galloping inflation, walking inflation, creeping inflation, demand-pull inflation and cost-push inflation. Some common causes of inflation include high cost of raw material, higher wage,

increase in money supply, higher taxes, low productivity, when demand is higher than supply, fall in the value of domestic currency, higher government spending during period of low revenue, expectation of increase in price, and so on.

Thus, inflation is a persistent and ongoing rise in the overall price of goods and services. Otherwise, inflation is a sustained and continuous fall in the value of money. Generally, some theories have been identified concerning the concept of inflation. According to the demand-pull paradigm, inflation occurs when the total demand for goods and services surpasses the total supply. This excess demand cannot be satisfied by gradually reducing current stockpiles, shifting supplies from the export to the domestic market, boosting imports, or delaying demand. According to the cost-push theory, rising manufacturing costs cause prices to rise. This theory continues that prices of goods and services rise because wages are strapped up by trade unions' negotiating power or by the pricing policies of oligopolistic and monopolistic firms with market power. The cost-push view credited inflation to a host of non-monetary supply-oriented influences of shocks that raise costs and, consequently, prices. Recently, this school of thought attributed inflation to random non-monetary shocks such as crop failures, commodity shortages, whims of weather, and oil price increases (Efanga, Ugwuanyi, & Umoh, (2020)).

Chhibber, & Shafik, (1990). Maintained that "wage push inflation is rare in Africa" because wages constitute only a small part of national income. However, this might not be true of Nigeria as any rise in wages simultaneously triggers upward prices of goods and services. The structuralists explained the long-run inflationary trends in developing countries regarding structural rigidities, market imperfection and social tension, relative inelasticity of food supply, foreign exchange constraints protective measures, rise in demand for food, fall in export earnings, and political instabilities. Unarguably, monetarists opined that "inflation is always and allover a monetary phenomenon resulting from and accompanied

by a rise in the quantity of money relative to output." Hence, prices can rise when the rate of inflation in money supply is larger than the rate of increase in actual output of goods and services. On the contrary, imported inflation arises as a result of international trade, where inflation is transmitted from one country to another, particularly during rising prices worldwide (Anyanwu, 1992). These paradigms support some reasons why Nigeria's inflation rate is high, but the monetarist's view has gained prominence. In this affection, an empirical investigation of the determinants of inflation is essential. The high inflation rate has become a significant concern because the poverty rate has increased (Olatunji, Omotesho, Ayinde & Ayinde, 2010).

Inflation in Nigeria

But today in Nigeria, the main driver of inflation is the fall in the value of Naira against other currency, particularly US dollar. As at recently, Nigerian Naira in the black market was selling at the range of about 1500 Naira to 2000 Naira to a dollar. This has been the lowest value Naira has ever attended in our lifetime. Since Nigeria depends for most of its things on importation from abroad, and dollar the main currency for international trade is falling rapidly, then the price of import is going to be high as we are seeing today. In the last few years, Nigeria has also experienced the problems of decline in revenue and increase in foreign debt (Abdullahi, 2018). Central Bank of Nigeria management of Naira is also not desirable. In the past especially in the 1970s, Nigeria had experienced serious cases of inflation. The main cause of the inflation during the period has been associated with increase in government revenue as a result of increase in oil revenue. This was followed by increase in government expenditure which came with large expansion in aggregate demand (Aiyede, 2002). Government measures such as Udoji salary awards were blamed for the inflationary crisis (Anyanwu, 1992).

Inflation around the World

Around the world there is growing inflation since the emergence of COVID-19 and the start of Russia-Ukraine war. The COVID-19 has

affected production of goods and services leading to scarcity around the world. Both Russia and Ukraine are very important in the supply of food and energy in the world. The start of war between the two countries has led to cut in the supply of food and energy around the world. Country like Venezuela experienced one of the highest inflation rates around the world. According World Bank report, oil price shocks is one of the major causes of inflation in the world. According to the report, oil price contributes about 38% of global inflation. Another cause of inflation around the world named by the report is global interest. For example, a country like Indonesia was affected by Russia-Ukraine war to the extent of causing increase in the price of food items. But despite that inflation rate, in Indonesia inflation is lower than in Nigeria. Inflation rate in Indonesia is in the range of 2.5% to 3%.

Empirical Literature Review

Numerous researches are being conducted to investigate the factors that influence different macroeconomic indicators. Research on the causes of inflation is becoming increasingly popular, and authors attempt to identify its causes using various methods. The subject of the study of most authors is one specific country or zone; a small part of the contributions is focused on groups of countries, including developed and emerging economies. In most studies, the global output gap, the domestic output gap, the exchange rate, and interest rates appear to be important indicators of inflation.

Adeleye, et al, (2019) have studied the internal and external drivers of inflation in Nigeria. They employed Johansen cointegration analysis, the vector error correction mechanism and the impulse response function for the analysis using data from 1981 to 2017. The results of the study blamed external factors for causing inflation in Nigeria; in particular the study blamed exchange rate, imported inflation and openness for causing inflation. Inim, et al (2020) analyzed determinants of inflation in Nigeria using ARDL model. They used quarterly data with the range January 1999 to December 2018. The results

show that apart from monetary variables, other factors such as infrastructure, political stability, corruption and taxation affect inflation. Olatunji, et al, (2010) examined determinants of inflation in Nigeria using time series data and cointegration method of analysis. The results show that export has negative effects on inflation while import has positive effects on inflation. Abdullahi, et al, (2022) have studied the effects of government expenditure on inflation, unemployment, consumption and investment in Nigeria during the period 1981 to 2020. The study used ARDL error correction model and granger causality for the analysis. The results of the analysis show that in the long run both recurrent and capital expenditures have negative effects on inflation; but they have positive effects on inflation in the short run.

Odusanya and Atanda (2010) analyzed dynamic relationship between inflation and its determinants between 1970 and 2007 using cointegration method of analysis. The results indicate that substantial benefits will come from moving from high inflation rate to low rate of inflation. Alexander, et al, (2015) have investigated determinants of inflation in Nigeria during the period 1986 – 2011 using Granger causality, VAR and cointegration methods. The results show that fiscal deficits, exchange rate, imports, money supply and agricultural output have long run effects on inflation. But, only the lending rate influenced inflation in both the short and long run. Iya and Aminu (2014) analysed the determinants of inflation in Nigeria between 1980 to 2012 using Granger causality and Cointegration analysis. The results of the analysis show that there exists causation between inflation and its determinants. Some of these determinants include money supply, government expenditure, exchange rate and interest rate. The cointegration result shows existence of long term relationship between inflation and the determinants. Shuaibu, et al, (2021) measured the effects of public debt on inflation and unemployment in Nigeria in the period 1985 to 2020. They used ARDL error correction model and granger causality tests for the analysis. The results of the analysis show

absence of relationship between public debt and inflation in Nigeria.

Ahamba, K. O., et al (2020) examined macroeconomic determinants of inflation in Nigeria employing annual time series data from 1981 to 2017. The study employed two inflation models based on the traditional “demand-pull and cost-push” theories, respectively, and applied autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) technique based on the outcome of Augmented Dickey-Fuller, Phillips-Perron, and breakpoint unit root tests, which revealed that the variables are integrated of different order. The ARDL bounds test result shows evidence of a long-run relationship among the variables in the existence of structural break in the series. This required the estimation of ARDL short-run and long-run results. The results of both models revealed that gross domestic product, money supply, general government expenditure, imports of goods and services, exchange rate, wages, interest rate, pump price of premium motor spirit, and unemployment rate are significant determinants of inflation in Nigeria.

Alexander, Andow, & Danpome, (2015) have analyzed the main determinants of inflation in Nigeria from 1986 – 2011. The co-integration result discloses the long-run equilibrium relationship between the inflation rate and its determinants. The Granger causality test found evidence of a feedback relationship between inflation and its causes. The estimated VAR result demonstrated the long-term effects of fiscal deficits, exchange rates, imports of products and services, money supply, and agricultural output on Nigeria's inflation rate. Loan rates solely impacted inflation during both the short and long term. The variance decomposition and impulse response data show that all the equation variables have significant variation and innovations due to "own shocks." It is clear that monetary and fiscal policy impact inflation in Nigeria.

Efanga, Ugwuanyi, & Umoh, (2020) have empirically ascertained the impact of inflation on Nigeria's economic growth, employing annual time series data generated from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin between 1981 and

2018. The data was modeled and analyzed using the Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Model. Other diagnostic tests such as the unit root test, test of normality, autocorrelation test, heteroskedasticity test, and Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation LM test were also carried out, and the validity and reliability of the model employed were confirmed. Real gross domestic product was employed as the explained variable, inflation was used as the explanatory variable, and the exchange rate was employed as the controlled variable. The results elicited from the study suggested that the inflation rate had a substantial negative impact on Nigerian economic growth. In contrast, the exchange rate recorded a negative and insignificant effect on Nigerian economic growth. This study concluded that inflation is dangerous to the economy of Nigeria; as such, it must be curbed.

Charles, Gilbert, & Emerenini, (2022) studied the determinants of inflation in Nigeria using annual time series data covering from 1981-2017. This period has been prudently selected to captures the different eras of policy implementation in Nigeria, such as the pre-SAP era, SAP era, and post-SAP era; it is long enough to assess The study objectively applied (ARDL). The ARDL bounds test result provided evidence of a stronghold long-run relationship among the variables. This necessitated the estimation of ARDL's short-run and long-run results. The short-run results of both models revealed that YGAP, M2, TGE, TIMP, and UEMPR were significant determinants of inflation in Nigeria. In contrast, the long-run results indicated that TGE, TIMP, and UEMPR were significant determinants of inflation in Nigeria. The impact of YGAP, M2, TGE, and TIMP was positive in both long and short runs, whereas YGAP, TIMP, TGE, and UEMPR negatively impacted inflation in both periods. The outcome of all the diagnostic tests supported the acceptability of the models' results. The study concludes that demand-pull and cost-push factors are responsible for Nigeria's inflation and provide the social infrastructure that would encourage private investment.

Data and Methodology

Data

Data was collected for the period 1989 to 2022. Data was sourced from National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), Central Bank of Nigeria and World Bank's Human Development Index. The individual data are for inflation, money supply, foreign debt, interest rate, exchange rate, import, export, foreign direct investment (FDI) and government expenditure. The data used for the study is time series data. Time series data are important for measuring secular trend, describing movement along the term; seasonal variations, representing seasonal changes; cyclical fluctuations, corresponding to periodical but not seasonal variations; irregular variations, which are other nonrandom sources of variations of series.

Method of Analysis

The method of analysis used for the work is cointegration analysis. Cointegration is an econometric method of analysis that measures relationship between two or more time-related series. A time-related series is several data points where one measurement is time. For example, the number of TV sets purchases by demographic from 1980 to date. The cointegration tests are used to find the degree of sensitivity of two variables or more to the same average value over a period of time. Cointegration method of analysis is aim at uncovering causal relations between variables through determining whether stochastic trends in a group of variables are shared by the series. There are a number of differences between correlation and cointegration. For example, a cointegrated series can have low correlation; in addition, a strongly correlated time series may not be cointegrated. Correlation simply describes a short-term relationship between variables; while cointegration describes a long-term relationship between them. Cointegration is said to occur when two or more non-stationary time series have a long-run equilibrium relationship. In other words, they move together such that their linear combination results in a stationary time series. They share an underlying common stochastic trend. The

concept of cointegration was introduced by Robert Engle and Clive Granger in 1987. There are many methods of testing for cointegration in data series. Some of the most common method of measuring for cointegration are: Engle–Granger two-step method, Johansen test, Phillips–Ouliaris cointegration test, Multicointegration, Variable shifts in long time series and Bayesian inference.

The other method of analysis used for the study is granger causality test. Granger causality is a test used in statistical and econometric studies to find out the usefulness of one variable in forecasting a different variable. An economic variable is said to Granger-cause another variable when it is good for forecasting the other variable. For example, a time series W is said to Granger-cause Z when it can be demonstrated, normally by means of series of t-tests and F-tests on lagged values of W (including lagged values of Y), that those W values give statistically significant explanation about future values of Z . Another statistical tool of analysis used for the study is correlation analysis. Correlation Analysis is statistical/econometric method of data analysis that is usually employed to find out if there is a relationship between two variables, and the level of strength of the relationship. The three main methods of measuring correlation are Spearman, Kendall and Pearson. In addition to these stationarity tests are conducted to find out the level of stationarity in the variables under study.

Empirical Model

The empirical model is of the form:

$$\text{INF} = f(\text{MS}, \text{FD}, \text{ITR}, \text{EXR}, \text{IMP}, \text{EXP}, \text{GEX}, \text{FDI}) \quad (1)$$

Where,

INF = Inflation

MS = Money supply

FD = Foreign debt

ITR = Interest rate

EXR = Exchange rate

IMP = Import

EXP = Export

GEX = Government expenditure

FDI = Foreign direct investment

Discussion of Results

Stylized Facts

Table 1 provides summary statistics about the variables used in the study. The variables are inflation, money supply, foreign debt, interest rate, exchange rate, import, export, foreign direct investment (FDI) and government expenditure.

Table 1. Summary Statistics

	INF	MS	FD	EXR	ITR	IMP	GEX	EXP01	FDI
Mean	19.04059	103.6974	41159570	142.4576	11.64465	3.65E+10	1.49E+10	4.58E+10	3193.458
Median	12.94500	28.27500	33810685	128.9350	10.48793	2.73E+10	1.01E+10	3.72E+10	2239.045
Maximum	72.84000	699.7300	98335334	425.9800	23.99000	9.40E+10	3.78E+10	1.45E+11	8914.890
Minimum	5.390000	1.040000	18576100	7.360000	4.704871	4.71E+09	4.88E+08	6.71E+09	-186.7900
Std. Dev.	16.81664	171.8731	19838356	117.3104	5.226022	2.84E+10	1.45E+10	3.63E+10	2445.012
Skewness	1.924004	2.056182	1.625432	0.856925	0.918895	0.418873	0.337361	1.048436	1.017905
Kurtosis	5.546991	6.392729	4.634522	2.957505	2.971596	1.780441	1.459568	3.368217	2.938312
Jarque-Bera	30.16698	40.26470	18.75636	4.163710	4.785895	3.101284	4.006590	6.420978	5.876795
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000085	0.124699	0.091360	0.212112	0.134890	0.040337	0.052951
Sum	647.3800	3525.710	1.40E+09	4843.560	395.9181	1.24E+12	5.05E+11	1.56E+12	108577.6
Sum Sq. Dev.	9332.383	974831.7	1.30E+16	454137.0	901.2732	2.66E+22	6.99E+21	4.35E+22	1.97E+08
Observations	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34

Source: Authors' analysis using Eview

Correlation

The results of the correlation analysis show that money supply has positive effect on

consumption while depreciation in the value of Naira tends to increase inflation.

Table 2. Correlation Analysis

Covariance Analysis: Ordinary									
Date: 04/22/24 Time: 06:51									
Sample: 1 34									
Included observations: 34									
Correlation									
Probability	INF	MS	FD	EXR	ITR	IMP	GEX	EXP01	FDI
INF	1.000000								

MS	0.230371	1.000000							
	0.1899	-----							
FD	-0.105182	-0.215116	1.000000						
	0.5538	0.2218	-----						
EXR	-0.366250	-0.412305	0.857969	1.000000					
	0.0331	0.0154	0.0000	-----					
ITR	0.535996	0.145792	-0.311615	-0.607441	1.000000				
	0.0011	0.4107	0.0728	0.0001	-----				
IMP	-0.432191	-0.460606	0.529597	0.768353	-0.679566	1.000000			
	0.0107	0.0061	0.0013	0.0000	0.0000	-----			
GEX	-0.424265	-0.474097	0.313781	0.617020	-0.657311	0.912536	1.000000		
	0.0124	0.0046	0.0707	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000	-----		

EXP01	-0.420322	-0.467662	0.118961	0.430548	-0.619718	0.814304	0.862157	1.000000	
	0.0133	0.0053	0.5028	0.0110	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000	-----	
FDI	-0.285634	-0.371542	-0.325183	0.064891	-0.415890	0.478719	0.660775	0.731790	1.000000
	0.1015	0.0305	0.0606	0.7154	0.0144	0.0042	0.0000	0.0000	-----

Source: Authors' analysis using Eview

Results of Granger Causality

The results of the granger causality tests show that there is no presence of short run causality

between inflation and its determinants. Table 3 provides the results of the granger causality test.

Table 3. Granger Causality Analysis

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests			
Date: 04/22/24 Time: 06:52			
Sample: 1 34			
Lags: 2			
Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
MS does not Granger Cause INF	32	0.18844	0.8293
INF does not Granger Cause MS		2.97849	0.0678
FD does not Granger Cause INF	32	0.07996	0.9234
INF does not Granger Cause FD		0.29877	0.7442
EXR does not Granger Cause INF	32	0.87873	0.4269
INF does not Granger Cause EXR		0.75935	0.4777
ITR does not Granger Cause INF	32	15.9118	3.E-05
INF does not Granger Cause ITR		2.26363	0.1234
IMP does not Granger Cause INF	32	0.88800	0.4232
INF does not Granger Cause IMP		0.08800	0.9160
GEX does not Granger Cause INF	32	0.63846	0.5359
INF does not Granger Cause GEX		0.35026	0.7077
EXP01 does not Granger Cause INF	32	1.15066	0.3315
INF does not Granger Cause EXP01		0.14809	0.8631
FDI does not Granger Cause INF	32	0.93915	0.4034
INF does not Granger Cause FDI		0.16642	0.8476

Source: Authors' analysis using Eview

Results of Cointegration Analysis

Table 4 show the results of cointegration test conducted between inflation and its determinants. As usual the determinants are inflation, money supply, foreign debt, interest rate, exchange rate, import, export, foreign direct investment (FDI) and government expenditure.

The results of the cointegration analysis show that interest rate is statistically significant and has negative effects on inflation. Import also is statistically significant with positive effects on consumption. The results also show that money supply, foreign debt, exchange rate, export, government expenditure and foreign direct investment are not statistically significant.

Table 4. Results of Cointegration Analysis

Variable	Coefficient	P-Value
Money Supply	0.011847	0.3409
Foreign Debt	1.52E-07	0.6835
Exchange Rate	-0.054383	0.4500
Interest Rate	-0.811637	0.0340
Import	1.86E-10	0.0471
Export	4.40E-11	0.7147
Government Expenditure	4.72E-10	0.3669
Foreign Direct Investment	-0.001882	0.1441

Source: Authors' analysis using Eview

The results mean that increase in interest rate tend to reduce inflation while decrease in interest

rate tend to increase inflation. The results also show that imports tend to cause inflation; with an increase in imports increasing the level of inflation in Nigeria while reduction of imports reduces inflation. This explains the external cause of inflation through importation. These results call for an increase in interest rate and reduction in imports in order to fight inflation. This is called for synergy between the Central Bank of Nigeria and the Ministry of Finance in order to fight the inflation menace. High interest rates on deposits make people deposit their money in banks in order to earn higher interest; this has the effect of reducing the amount of money in circulation. While with deterioration in the exchange rate over the years, the importation of foreign goods and services into Nigeria tends to be inflationary.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper analyses the major determinants of inflation in Nigeria during the period 1989 to 2022. It analysed the impacts of the following factors on inflation in Nigeria: money supply, foreign debt, interest rate, exchange rate, import, export, foreign direct investment (FDI) and government expenditure. The results of the study show that inflation in Nigeria during the period of the study is as a result of monetary and fiscal policy defects; especially government's interest rate and import policies. But, in the short run period the main determinants of inflation have not much effect on inflation. As a result, inflation has proven itself to be a destroyer of people's hopes and plans in Nigeria in the last few years. It has so far impoverished the large majority of households in Nigeria. In order to fight the menace of inflation in Nigeria, both the CBN and the Ministry of Finance must join hands to fight it. Only by coordination between monetary authorities and fiscal authorities will the problem of inflation be controlled effectively. The following measures can help reduce inflation in Nigeria: increase in the value of Naira against other currencies, reduction of importation of goods and services that we can produce in Nigeria, increase local production of goods and services, government shall reduce unnecessary spending, reduction in money supply, increase

farm production, reduction of taxes and tariffs, reduction in the price of energy, promotion of saving and investment, increase in capital and boost in productivity.

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